

The Early Development of Stereochemistry and Pasteur's Law. *

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The Chemical Society of London, founded in 1841, is the oldest existing society devoted to the furtherance of chemistry. In the earlier years of this society's life, according to Dr. Scott's presidential remarks of 1916, it was thought sufficient for the President to read extracts from the report of the Council, sometimes adding comments on the balance sheet, which hardly filled two pages of the Journal. But with the passage of years, more and more was expected from the President until now, at each anniversary meeting, he is required to deliver a formal address on some subject closely connected with the life of the society as "a body politic and corporate," or on some subject of more purely scientific interest.

The Indian Chemical Society, which came into existence in 1924, was founded with similar aims and objects. Its anniversary meeting is held, in conjunction with the annual gathering of the Indian Science Congress, at different centres of learning with the express purpose of affording an opportunity to its Fellows, scattered all over the country, to take a more active interest in all its affairs. During the first seven years of its existence, both of my predecessors, who have occupied the chair, have set the precedent of delivering presidential addresses on purely scientific subjects.

It is my intention to-day to follow this precedent, and to divide my address into two parts. The first of these will deal with the development of stereochemistry from early times. The second part will deal with what is known as Pasteur's Law, and will contain comments on the results obtained in the chemical laboratory of the Ravenshaw College, Cuttack, on the physical identity of enantiomers—a subject of fundamental importance in the study of optical activity.

Stereochemistry is an experimental branch of the chemical science, and may be regarded as securely founded on the experi-

* Presidential address delivered on the Eighth Annual General Meeting of the Indian Chemical Society, held on the 4th January, 1932 at Bangalore.

mental investigations and theoretical speculations of Pasteur, Kekulé, Le Bel and Van't Hoff. Stereochemical speculations, however, have been prevalent in chemistry since olden times. One of the six schools of Hindu Philosophy—Vaiśeṣika or Atomic Philosophy founded by Kaṇāda†—deals with the atomic theory of matter. The whole universe and the material substances are aggregates of atoms; the atoms are imperishable, the aggregates perish by disintegration. The law of the conservation of matter follows as a necessary corollary from this doctrine. It is thus seen that from very early times in the history of science, matter was believed to be permanent‡, incapable of either annihilation or of creation.

The atomic theory of matter was revived at a much later period by the great classical thinkers of Greece, Leucippus and his successor Democritus (about 460—360 B.C.). Atoms are non-creatable, indestructible and non-changeable. Plato (427—347 B.C.) gave definite geometrical forms to this original matter and thus assigned to it a condition of corporal reality.

Epicurus (341—270 B.C.) assumed all bodies to be modifications of a single homogeneous primary matter. He assigned definite forms to the particles of matter, which was permanent, and of an unchangeable nature. These ideas of the early Greek philosophers were incorporated by the Roman poet Titus Lucritius Carus (96—55 B.C.) in his poetical work, "*De rerum natura*". The problem of the size, weight and form of the atoms was now thrown into the background for lack of experimental data concerning them, and the idea of a *materia prima* captivated the minds of later philosophers. So more than a thousand years passed away without any advance being made

† According to Sir Radha Krishnan, whatever may be the date of Kaṇāda, he is only a systematiser of views which have had a long growth prior to him. He does not believe that his atomic conceptions themselves were later than the time of Leucippus and Democritus (*Indian Philosophy*, Vol. 2, pp. 202-203).

‡ Though the doctrine of the permanence of matter has been accepted from the times of the early Hindu and Greek thinkers, supporters of the opposite idea have never been wanting. In modern times, they are even found among followers of the 'experimental philosophy'. Sir James Jeans is a strong advocate of this opposite idea, and has ably summarised the evidence—astronomical and physical—in support of it (*Nature*, 1921, 125, 103). The annihilation of matter, according to the astronomical evidence, seems to be the only possible source of the energy radiated by the stars, and thus constitutes one of the fundamental processes of the universe. It must, however, be admitted that this hypothesis awaits further observational and experimental data for its final assessment.

in this direction, till we reach the seventeenth century, when the German chemist, Sennert, once more revives the idea that all matter is made up of unchangeable, elementary corpuscles. According to Descartes, (1596—1650), matter is characterised by dimensions, the ultimate particles of matter are the corpuscles, that is the smallest bodies which differ in form and size. Gassendi (1592—1650), a contemporary of Descartes, was also an active supporter of the old atomic theory. According to him, there is a limit to the divisibility of matter, and the ultimate particles of this division are called atoms, which possess size, form and weight. The atoms unite in different ways to form molecules. It appears that the conception of molecules is used here for the first time.

Three chemists were largely responsible for introducing spatial ideas into chemistry as a mental aid. They were Glauber (1604-1670), Boyle (1627-1691), and Lemery (1645-1715). Glauber, a great chemical manipulator and an experimenter, was probably one of the first to point out that crystal form is a characteristic of each salt type, and he recommended its use as a means of chemical identifications.¹

Boyle pictured his atoms provided with points, hooks and pores owing to the preference given to physiological reactions as a means of recognition of substances in general. The words, "sour", "alkaline" and "salty" are even to-day used as qualitative attributes for chemical substances, being derived from the sensation of taste. Boyle's definition of a salt, "It is easily dissoluble in water, and it affects the palate with a savour whether good or evil", clearly reflects the attitude of mind of the corpuscular chemists, which ascribed to the corpuscles or atoms, the forms of sharp and pointed tools from the analogy of certain mechanical effects which brought forth like sensations.

Boyle in his "Sceptical Chymist", published in 1661, gives further expression to these corpuscular views thus: "Whatever may be the number of elements, one may some day probably be able to demonstrate that they exist as indefinable particles, nevertheless begotten of definite form and size, and that it is the arrangement and combination of these corpuscles which gives rise to the manifold number and varieties of bodies". According to him acids dissolve metals when the pointed particles of the first are congruous with those of the latter. He compares acid particles to knife blades; some of these have only one end encased in a shield; in the case of others

both ends have been put into a shield. The existence of the two chlorides of mercury for instance, is accounted for in this mechanical fashion.

The French chemist, Lemery, propounded his mechanistic corpuscular theory in his book "Cours de Chimie", which first appeared in 1675. This work which had been published in no less than six European languages exerted a profound influence for about a century on the theory of atoms and corpuscles. Chemical character and chemical reactions were determined by spatial factors, *i.e.*, by the form and size of particles. "Acidity of a fluid is due to the presence of pointed particles. An acid is made up of pointed components". The strength of acids was regarded as dependent upon the size and kind of "points" on the particles. The reaction between a given acid and an alkali was thus a question of steric agreement or steric hindrance.

Salt formation through the action of acids upon metals, such as silver nitrate from silver and nitric acid is according to Lemery, an operation in which "the metal is penetrated and reduced to the form of salt by the points of the acid." It is thus seen that the believers in the corpuscular theory of matter regarded the form of corpuscles as the deciding factor in differentiating different kinds of salts, acids, and bases.

The great development in mechanics in the seventeenth century associated with the names of Galileo, Kepler and Newton, exerted a powerful influence, and chemists of that period were not slow in giving mechanical explanations of chemical phenomena. The mechanical ideas, however, did not prove quite satisfactory in explaining chemical phenomena. When an acid acts on a metal, the particles of both come into immediate contact. So far the process can be regarded as mechanical, but further mechanical explanation is lacking as to what takes place *after* the reacting particles of the acid and metal collide with one another.

It should be mentioned that protest against these mechanistic explanations with the aid of points, thorns, pores, screws, clasps, etc., of the particles was not wanting even at that time. It was made by John Kunckel, the great physician, in his book, "Laboratorium Chymicum" (p. 133) published in 1722.

It is, however, interesting to note that mechanics once more, in these days, is coming into closer relationship with chemistry. These newer ideas are based not on the classical mechanics of the seven-

teenth century, but on the modern theory of wave-mechanics or quantum-mechanics associated with the names of Broglie, Heisenberg and Schrödinger.

We have seen that the speculations of the seventeenth century had attempted to solve the question of the form of particles by means of a mechanistic hypothesis. The eighteenth century supplied a new scientific weapon, namely crystallography, in obtaining definite evidence concerning *form* itself. Two French crystallographers stand out as great pioneers in this development, *e.g.*, Romé de l'Isle and René J. Haüy. The latter correlated crystalline form and chemical composition. This early crystallographic work proved of great value in the succeeding century in the formulation of ideas regarding the spatial arrangement of atoms in the molecule.

In 1808 Dalton published his "New System of Chemical Philosophy" and propounded fundamental concepts of great importance, namely, the atomic theory and the laws of chemical combination. In the same year Wollaston² introduced spatial ideas about atoms. He says "We shall find that the arithmetical relation alone will not be sufficient to explain their mutual action, and we shall be obliged to acquire a geometrical conception of their relative arrangement in all three dimensions of solid extension". The molecular theory developed by Ampère and Avogadro in conjunction with crystallography, was instrumental in extending these ideas of spatial arrangement of atoms. The association of the idea of a spatial environment with the structure of an organic molecule began to be more commonly accepted as a mental picture as is seen in Laurent's kernel theory (1837). It was based on Haüy's theory of crystal structure. Leopold Gmelin³ deserves much credit for giving us for the first time, a clear account of stereochemical conceptions. He directed attention to the idea of relative position of atoms in the molecule, as this may lead us to arrive at a proper conception of the constitution of organic compounds.

The discovery of the Law of Isomorphism by E. Mitscherlich⁴ in 1819 "Crystal form is independent of the chemical nature of atoms and is determined only by the number and relative position of the atoms" was of very great assistance in fixing the relative atomic weights of elements, and thus gave great stimulus to the development of the Atomic Theory. The discovery of the phenomenon of isomerism by Gay-Lussac⁵ soon after—according to which substances may exist which have the same composition, but which may

be different physically and chemically—proved to be of immense value in the evolution of the theory of molecular structure of organic compounds. The synthesis of urea from ammonium cyanate by Wöhler in 1828—the first classical example of an organic product built up in the laboratory—broke down the distinction of a 'vital force' in the chemistry of living and non-living matter. This is also one of the earliest examples of a pair of isomeric substances. Rapid strides which were now made in organic synthesis led to a remarkable increase in the number of isomeric compounds. The older theories of structure were found to be inadequate to accommodate all this new knowledge of isomeric phenomena, and led Kekulé in 1858 to propound his theory of molecular structure, based on the hypothesis of valency and the law of linking of atoms. As is often the case in the history of this subject, this great development was brought about by Kekulé when he was only 29 years old. The circumstances under which he got the inspiration are recorded by him in a speech^{5a} before the German Chemical Society. "One fine summer evening I was returning by the last omnibus, 'outside' as usual, through the deserted streets of the metropolis (London), which are at other times so full of life. I fell into a reverie (Traümerie), and lo, the atoms were gambolling before my eyes. Whenever, hitherto, these diminutive beings had appeared to me, they had always been in motion; but up to that time, I had never been able to discern the nature of their motion. Now, however, I saw how, frequently two smaller atoms united to form a pair; how a larger one even embraced two smaller ones; how still larger ones kept held of three or even four of the smaller; whilst the whole kept whirling in a giddy dance". As a result of the great advance made by Kekulé, the conception of molecular constitution followed as a necessary corollary of this new doctrine, and led to clearer ideas about the constitution of chemical compounds by means of their graphic formulae. The theoretical scheme of Kekulé proved, however, insufficient to embrace all the known facts, until in 1874, Van't Hoff and Le Bel, independently demonstrated the all important part which molecular configuration plays in the interpretation of certain cases of isomerism in organic chemistry. The evolution of the theory of molecular structure into that of molecular configuration was brought about by the discovery of two pairs of acids, which were destined to play an important part in the development of stereochemical ideas, namely, racemic acid (Gay-Lussac, 1826) isomeric with tartaric acid, and lactic acid (Scheele,

1780) isomeric with paralactic acid or sarcolactic acid. This advance is due to the crystallographic investigations of Pasteur (1848-1860) on the first pair of acids and their salts. Previous to this in 1841 de La Provostaye had carefully determined the crystal forms of tartaric and racemic acids and their salts. Mitscherlich in 1844 published the results of his crystallographic examination of the sodium-ammonium salts of racemic and tartaric acids, stating that these double salts "have the same chemical composition, same crystalline form and angles, identical specific weights and double refraction, in consequence of which their axes form the same angles. Their aqueous solutions have the same refraction. However, the dissolved tartrate rotates the plane of polarised light, whereas the other is indifferent, a fact which had previously been noted for this whole series of salts by Biot". "But", continues Mitscherlich, "*the nature and the number of atoms, their arrangement and their distance from one another are the same in both bodies*"⁶. This conclusion, at the time of its publication, especially concerned Pasteur who was then only 22 years old, and was still studying at the Ecole Normale, and four years later acted as a stimulus for a whole series of new experimental and theoretical investigations. But the course of development of Pasteur's ideas, culminating in his theory of Molecular Dissymmetry, is logical and is yet another instance which illustrates that the progress of chemistry has been mainly achieved as the result of the co-ordination of observed facts with a series of hypotheses, each closely related in point of time to the one preceding it. It also shows the truth of the remarks of Laplace, "The essence of a discovery lies in the combination of ideas that are fit for combination, and that were hitherto isolated." An account of this development of ideas has been left to us by Pasteur in his two famous lectures⁷, "Concerning the asymmetry of naturally occurring organic compounds," delivered before the Chemical Society of Paris in 1860. His theory of molecular asymmetry is the foundation on which modern stereochemistry rests. At the time of his researches, the theory of molecular structure of Kekulé* had not come into existence. It was,

* The lack of this knowledge is reflected in an error, which Pasteur made in connection with his researches on malic acid. He erroneously concluded that every asymmetric substance must exist in four different forms (Lectures on molecular dissymmetry, 1860). The number of isomeric forms into which an asymmetric molecule may exist, cannot always be predicted without a knowledge of its structural formula, which was, however, unknown at that time. Even this error led him to discover the fourth tartaric acid, namely, the meso, the internally compensated variety.

therefore, not possible to depict structurally the organic compounds by the graphical representation of atomic linkage, and even the two dimensional formulae, limited as they are as a true picture of the molecule, were unknown at that time. His studies on the influence of molecular asymmetry of natural organic products on living matter is the direct outcome of his early crystallographic work, and is a most surprising chapter of stereochemistry," "which," he says, "opens up a new, distant, but definite horizon for physiology."

We should now revert to consider this early development of ideas in the mind of Pasteur and follow closely his line of thought. Haüy and Weiss recognised the occurrence of hemihedral faces upon quartz and that these faces in certain individuals lay to the right and in others to the left. Biot (1813) had found that quartz crystals could be divided into two groups as regards their behaviour towards polarised light ; one turned the plane of polarised light to the right, the other to the left, but to an equal extent. Two years later he discovered that organic liquids (oil of turpentine) and aqueous solutions of tartaric acid and sugar also possess optical activity. Biot further showed in 1817 that matter in the gaseous state also exhibited this property, as in the case of the vapour of turpentine. The property of optical activity is thus exhibited by matter in all the three states of aggregation, solid, liquid and gaseous. Herschell subsequently (1820) correlated these hitherto isolated facts by suggesting a connection between the crystal form and optical rotation; and the thought was fully confirmed by experiment in that those quartz crystals with right hemihedral faces turned the plane of polarised light to the right and those with left hemihedral faces turned the plane of polarised light to the left. Thus a fruitful relation between hemihedrism and optical rotation of crystalline substances (such as quartz, *etc.*) was discovered. Pasteur, at the outset of his brilliant scientific career repeated the previously mentioned investigation of de La Provostaye on the crystal form of tartaric acid, racemic acid and their salts. He discovered something which had been overlooked by the great physicist, namely that all crystals of the tartrate possessed hemihedral faces, and correlated this hemihedrism of the tartrates with the previous observations of Biot on their optical activity. He thus established the same kind of parallelism between hemihedrism and optical rotation for tartaric acid and tartrates, both in the crystalline state and in solution, as had previously been found by Herschell for quartz. Pasteur further investigated the crystal form of racemic

acid which showed no hemihedrism, and it had been shown by Biot that aqueous solution of this acid was inactive towards polarised light. In this way his first idea of a possible connection between the hemihedrism of the tartrates and their optical activity was converted into one of certainty, so far as Pasteur was concerned. But how were these facts to be brought into harmony with the previously mentioned observations of Mitscherlich, who had found in 1844 that the crystal forms of the sodium-ammonium salts of racemic and tartaric acids were completely identical? Pasteur, at once concluded that Mitscherlich had erred in one point. Apparently he had failed to observe that the double salt of tartaric acid is hemihedral, while that of racemic acid is not. In order to clear up this point, Pasteur repeated this work on the crystalline form of both of Mitscherlich's salts with the utmost care. He observed that the double salt of racemic acid crystallised with hemihedral faces, some of which were oriented to the right, others to the left. The two types of crystals were separated from one another, and their aqueous solutions of equal concentration were examined in the polarimeter. He then found with no less surprise than pleasure, that the solution of the salt with right hemihedral faces was *dextro*-rotatory, and that of the salt with left hemihedral character was *laevo*-rotatory to an equal extent, further, on mixing these two solutions, optical activity disappeared. The emotions which must have stirred the mind of the young investigator were so great that he was unable to remain at the polarimeter. These experiments were later repeated by Pasteur in the presence of Biot, and an account of the dramatic scene which ensued had been left on record by Pasteur himself ⁷. The illustrious old physicist was visibly moved so much that he seized Pasteur's hand and exclaimed: "My dear child, I have all my life so loved this science that I can hear my heart beat for joy". The correct explanation of these facts was given by Pasteur: on crystallising the optically inactive sodium-ammonium racemate, the salt must have separated into its *dextro*- and *laevo*-rotatory components. The *dextro*- and *laevo*-tartaric acids were obtained from the optically active salts in a pure state, and possessed equal and opposite rotation. When a mixture of equal weights of the two acids was crystallised, the product was identical with racemic acid. Pasteur's acute judgment at once led him to conclude that the molecules of the two tartaric acids were the same in composition and structure, differing in spatial arrangement such that one was the enantiomorph of the other. This

would be the case only, if their configurations were tridimensional, and were related to one another as an object is to its non-superposable mirror image, owing to the existence of "molecular dissymmetry". This view is altogether correct; it is of more universal application than the later view of Le Bel and Van't Hoff. Whenever the molecular configuration is such that it is different from its mirror image there is a possible isomerism in which the two isomers are related to one another as the right hand is to the left. In the solid state they show enantiomorphous crystals, and in solution opposite optical activity.

The above mentioned work on sodium-ammonium racemate enabled Pasteur to discover the first of his classical methods for the resolution of racemic substances into their optical antipodes. The second, salt formation by means of optically active bases, and subsequent fractional crystallisation, followed in 1853. The third method⁸, involving the destruction of one of the active forms by means of micro-organisms, was discovered in 1858.

As it is already pointed out, the theory of Kekulé had not yet been propounded, and therefore, it was not possible for Pasteur to point out more precisely the spatial arrangement of the atoms in the molecules. The insufficiency of two-dimensional formulae of Kekulé was gradually being recognised, and other suggestions of three-dimensional models of molecules were now forthcoming. Butlerow deserves special mention in this connection. He thus wrote in 1862, 'Let us take a simple example, and assuming that all four valency units of tetravalent carbon are different, let us give it the form of a tetrahedron, where each of the four surfaces may combine with one equivalent of hydrogen.'⁹ In 1863 he was even more decisive with the idea of spatial arrangement, when he said¹⁰, "If atoms really exist, I cannot see why all attempts at determining their spatial arrangement are useless, as Kolbe would have us believe. Why should not the future teach us how to make such determinations?" Even Kekulé, the inventor of two-dimensional formulae was not unaware of spatial models, when he said, "The incompleteness of the older models may be avoided, if the four valencies of carbon instead of being represented in a plane, are directed along the axes of a hexahedron starting from the atomic sphere itself and ending in the planes of a tetrahedron."¹¹ In 1869 several chemists put forward spatial ideas. Ladenburg's prism formula for benzene¹² and its representation by six tetrahedrons by Rosentiehl clearly involved spatial considerations. Wislicenus' work on the three modifi-

cations of lactic acid, which could not be explained on the two-dimensional formulae of Kekulé, forced him to write thus in this connection: "The facts compel us to explain the difference between isomeric molecules possessing the same structural formula by the different arrangement of their atoms in space."¹³

These ideas of spatial arrangement of the atoms in a molecule had taken definite hold of the mind of Van't Hoff, who was then only 22 years old. He gave them a mathematical form in his small pamphlet ^{13a}, published in Dutch in September, 1874. A mere detailed account of this work appeared in the following year, in the French language, under the title: "La chimie dans l'espace." The circumstances, under which the discovery of the idea of the asymmetric carbon atom were made, are thus given by Van't Hoff in 1904: "At that time (1873) I had been studying Wislicenus' paper on the lactic acids at the University of Utrecht, and when about half way through the article, I decided to stop my work, and take a walk. It was during this walk, under the influence of fresh air, that the idea of an asymmetric carbon atom occurred to me."

At about the same time (November, 1874) Le Bel ¹⁴ published independently similar views on molecular symmetry and optical rotation. The conceptions of the two young investigators were not quite the same. Van't Hoff based his theory on Kekulé's law of the quadrivalency of carbon with the added hypothesis of the tetrahedral environment of the four valencies of the carbon atom. Le Bel's starting point was the researches of Pasteur.

The Le Bel-Van't Hoff theory of the asymmetric carbon atom may be briefly stated thus: If a molecule contains a carbon atom linked to four different substituents, the spatial distribution around the atom becomes asymmetrical, and this may be effected in two different ways, the one being the non-superposable mirror image of the other. The conception of the asymmetric carbon atom involves the idea of the "chemical contrast" between the substituents as well as their dissymmetric spatial arrangement.

The doctrine of the asymmetric atom has done great service in the development of stereochemistry ^{14a}. It is a useful guide in deciding whether an optically inactive substance can be resolved into its optically active components. In this way, elements other than carbon were shown to furnish optically active substances in which the enantiomorphism is associated with the presence of an asymmetric

sulphur ¹⁵, selenium ¹⁶, tin ¹⁷, silicon ¹⁸, boron ¹⁹, nitrogen ²⁰, or phosphorus atom ²¹.

We may now cite cases to illustrate the inadequacy of the theory of the asymmetric atom by showing that the presence of such an atom in a molecule is not always a necessary condition for the occurrence of enantiomorphously related isomers. These cases include the complex metal compounds of Werner ²², Berylliumbenzoylpyruvic acid of Mills ²³, potassium disalicylborate of Boeseken ²⁴, 1-methylcyclohexylidene-4-acetic acid of Pope, Perkin and Wallach ²⁵, 6:6'-dinitrodiphenic acid and other compounds of the diphenyl series of Kenner ²⁶, and a derivative of 8-nitro-1-naphthylamine of Mills ²⁷:

(in which $R_1 = C_6H_5SO_2$ - and $R_2 = -CH_2 \cdot COOH$).

Another class of molecularly dissymmetric substances is formed by spirocyclic carbon compounds of the type

The first substance of this kind to be investigated was the ketodilactone of benzophenone-2:4:2':4'-tetracarboxylic acid ²⁸,

and this was followed by another representative of this class, namely, bisdihydrocarbostyryl-3:3'-spirane-6:6'-disulphonic acid ^{28a}.

A number of compounds of 3 co-valent sulphur obtained by Phillips ²⁹, which belong to the sulphonic esters,

$\begin{array}{c} R_1-S-R_2 \\ \downarrow \\ N \cdot SO_2R \end{array}$ are of very great interest, as the molecular dissymmetry of this group of compounds is brought about by only three radicles attached to the central atom.

In all cases, these compounds have been separated into their optically active antimers. It is thus evident that the Le Bel-Van't Hoff idea is only a very special case covered by Pasteur's more universal principle. It applies only to the case, not even a simple one, in which on account of the wholly asymmetric spatial distribution around one of the atoms, the molecule lacks all symmetry. The conception of Pasteur, however, covers all cases; those in which it is possible to single out an asymmetric atom, and others where molecule does not contain such an asymmetric atom, but possesses enantiomorphous molecular configuration brought about by a dissymmetric distribution in space even by identical substituents. The "chemical contrast" between the substituents involved in the Le Bel-Van't Hoff hypothesis is not absolutely necessary. It is possible for the molecule as a whole to show a non-superposable symmetry of its configuration, even if the substituents of the complex are identical. The remarkable series of optically active co-ordination compounds of the metals of which triethylenediamine cobaltic chloride $[Co'''(en)_3]Cl_3$ and potassium chrome oxalate $[Cr'''(C_2O_4)_3]K_3$ of Werner ²² are examples, form a class of substances in which the molecular dissymmetry is associated with very great degree of symmetry of chemical constitution brought about by identical substituents.

Pasteur's Law: The Absolute Identity of the Physical and Chemical Properties of Enantiomers.

As already mentioned, Pasteur through his brilliant researches on racemic and tartaric acids discovered the special isomeric relations of the molecules of the same structural formula which are related to each other as an object is to its non-superposable mirror image. Though the great French Savant was not able

to indicate the precise spatial arrangement of the atom in the molecule, he, at once, realised that his epoch making discovery made it absolutely necessary to recognise the fact that any wholly successful representation of the organic molecule must be extended in tri-dimensional space. He significantly asks, " Are the atoms of the *dextro* acid arranged in the form of a right-handed spiral, or are they situated at the corners of an irregular tetrahedron, or do they have some other asymmetric grouping? This we do not know. But without doubt the atoms possess an asymmetric arrangement like that of an object and its reflected image " 7.

The Identity of Chemical Properties.—In this way, Pasteur was able to classify organic compounds into two great groups; symmetrical compounds with enantiomorphous reflected images. He showed that the identity of chemical properties in the case of enantiomorphous compounds, like the two tartaric acids and their derivatives, persists so long as they are brought together with bodies of the first category, e.g., potassium hydroxide, sodium hydroxide, ammonia, alcohols and ethers; in short with all bodies without asymmetry. With such bodies which are devoid of asymmetry, the enantiomorphous forms do not affect the action of chemical affinity.*

On the other hand, if they are subjected to the action of bodies of the second class, which are themselves asymmetric, then the two products which are formed no longer identical in their properties. They differ in solubility, crystalline form, specific gravity, and the amount of water of crystallisation, since they are no longer enantiomorphous, and may differ from one another quite as much as the most distantly related isomers. It is thus seen that molecular asymmetry may alter the action of chemical affinity. It will be seen that Pasteur discovered his second method (salt formation) of resolution of racemic compounds into their optically active components as the result of his theoretical speculations and the above mentioned close reasoning into the nature of molecular dissymmetry. It was not due to any chance occurrence, as is the case with his first (spontaneous crystallisation) and third (biochemical) method.

The Physical Identity of Enantiomers.—According to Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry, enantiomorphous molecular

* The velocity constant of mutarotation of the *d*- and *l*-oxymethylenecamphor in benzene solution is practically identical (Singh and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 771). This shows that the enantiomers are identical as regards the rate of chemical change involved in the process of mutarotation.

configurations must possess the same total energy. They must show similar mechanical stability, and, therefore, have an equal chance of being produced. They must also possess the same scalar properties, such as density, crystal lustre, solubility, refraction, dispersion. But they must differ in these physical properties, which are of the directional (vectorial) nature, such as, for example, direction of rotation of the plane of polarisation of polarised light, unsymmetrical distribution of the hemihedral facets in their crystal forms, and also in the enantiomorphous distribution of pyro- and piezo-electrical polarity. The magnitude of these vectorial properties is, however, identical for the enantiomorphous forms. These results follow from classical mechanics. On the other hand, according to wave-mechanics³⁰, the *dextro*- and *laevo*-forms of a compound differ in energy and in rotatory power, although perhaps only to a very slight extent. The two views thus lead to different results. In support of the view derived from wave-mechanics, slight but distinct differences are alleged to exist in the rotatory power and other physical properties of the *dextro*- and *laevo*-forms of mandelic and camphoric acids³¹. But Pasteur's Law of Molecular Dissymmetry is too fundamental to be dismissed by a few isolated observations; the discrepancies in these cases may very well be due to some impurities in the substances examined. It seems impossible that the *d*- and *l*-forms of a compound could be other than an object and its non-superposable exact mirror-image, agreeing precisely in every detail of structure and of properties, except those of a vectorial nature, which differ in sign, but otherwise identical in the *numerical magnitude* in all cases. Moreover it must be borne in mind that the wave-mechanics of rotatory polarisation is, at present, in a rather unsatisfactory condition.

With the object of testing the validity of Pasteur's Law as regards the equality in the numerical value of the rotatory power of the opposite active forms, an extended series of investigations on the rotatory dispersion of enantiomorphous forms was undertaken in 1926. The first paper on this subject was published in 1930, and since then seven communications³² have appeared in our Journal and in the Transactions of the Faraday Society. An equal number of papers dealing with this subject and other aspects of the problem still awaits publication. The compounds, which have been examined, belong to the aryl derivatives of iminocamphor, amino-

camphor, aminomethylenecamphor, and the corresponding bis derivatives of the following types (I-VI):

(I)

(II)

(III)

(R = a monovalent radicle).

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(X'' = a divalent radicle).

The rotatory powers of the *d*- and *l*-forms have been examined in six solvents for about eight wave-lengths in the visible region of the spectrum (λ 6708 to 4358 Å.U.) at 35° and at almost identical concentrations. Out of about 1600 observations on the rotatory power which have been recorded³² and those which still await publication, the differences in the specific rotatory power of the *dextro* and *laevo* forms correspond to a difference which is within 0.01° in the observed angle of rotation in 80 per cent. cases, between 0.01° and 0.02° in 17 per cent. cases, between 0.02° and 0.03° in 2.5 per cent. cases, and between 0.03° and 0.04° in the remaining one half per cent. cases, the maximum deviation allowable in such observations being 0.02° in the observed angle of rotation. The three per cent. cases, in which the differences are slightly greater than the maximum allowable deviation (0.02°) for certain wave-length, give values for rotatory power for other wave-lengths, which are within this

maximum error. This shows that these deviations are of the nature of casual experimental errors. By way of illustration, the rotatory dispersion of the *d*- and *l*-forms of aminomethylenecamphor³³ is given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Aminomethylenecamphor.

$t = 35^\circ$; $l = 2$ dcm.; solvent = pyridine.

Concentration (g. in 100 c.c.) of *d*-form = 3.0016,
 ,, ,, ,, *l*-form = 3.0024.

Line	<i>d</i> -form.		difference in [α] of <i>d</i> - and <i>l</i> -forms.	<i>l</i> -form	
	α	[α]		α	[α]
Cd ₅₀₈₆	+28.31°	471.7°	-0.3°	-28.34°	472.0°
Ag ₅₂₀₉	26.35	438.9	+0.1	26.35	438.8
Hg ₅₄₆₁	22.96	382°	-0.14	22.97	382.5
Hg ₅₇₂₀	19.58	326.15	-0.05	19.59	326.2
Na ₅₈₉₃	18.61	309.9	+0.4	18.60	309.5
Li ₆₁₀₄	16.93	282.1	-0.1	16.94	282.2
Cd ₆₄₃₈	14.74	245.5	-0.1	14.75	245.6
Li ₆₇₀₈	13.32	221.9	+0.05	13.32	221.85

The recent observations of Darmois³⁴ on the rotatory power of the *d*- and *l*-forms of the complex ammonium salts of molybdic and malic acids of the formula $[4 \text{ MoO}_3, 2 \text{ C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5] (\text{NH}_4)_4 + 5 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$, for mercury green light, show that the observed angles of rotation do not differ by more than 1 part in 1000 parts. This is also the accuracy attained with aminomethylenecamphors (Table I).

These results clearly support Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry, according to which the *d*- and *l*-forms are represented as true mirror images of one another, differing in sign, but absolutely identical in the numerical value of the rotatory power.

In conclusion, I wish to make an observation, which may serve to inspire and encourage younger chemists. It is this: on no account are they to be deterred from making bold speculations and experiments in fields which have already been trodden by more

experienced and older workers. It often happens that the latter have lost that plasticity of mind, which alone can produce or receive fruitful ideas. The account of the evolution of the theories of molecular configuration of organic compounds, which I have attempted to-day, shows that this subject has been exclusively developed, so far as fundamental concepts are concerned, by young men, at the very threshold of their career—Pasteur, Kekulé, Van't Hoff and Le Bel.

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